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ROLE OF $[W(CO)_6]$ IN ORGANIC REACTIONS

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Abstract

The special interest attached to the chemistry of metal carbonyls arises from several causes. While quite distinct from the metal carbonyls in the organometallic compounds, they differ in Physical properties (e.g., volatility) from all other compounds of the transition metals. Chemically, they constitute a group of compounds in which the formal valency of the metal atoms is zero, and in this respect they are comparable only with the recently discovered compounds. As a class, the metal carbonyls are reactive compounds, and a number of new types of inorganic compounds have been discovered. Carbon monoxide (CO) is an important building block in $M(CO)_6$ for the synthesis of many compounds.

Tungsten hexacarbonyl (also called tungsten carbonyl) is the chemical compound with the formula $W(CO)_6$. This complex gave rise to the first example of a dihydrogen Complex with an octahedral geometry consisting of six rod-like CO ligands radiating from the central W atom with dipole moment 0.0D. All reactions of $W(CO)_6$ commence with displacement of some CO ligands in $W(CO)_6$. It can be used as a precursor to catalysts for alkene metathesis and in ligand substitution reactions. $W(CO)_6$ are also a popular reagent in organometallic synthesis, because one or more CO ligands can be displaced by other donor ligands. Because the catalyst and precursors are sensitive to air, all $W(CO)_6$ catalyzed reactions must be carried out under an inert atmosphere. $W(CO)_6$ is found their important role in finding some specific products. The successful development of metal carbonyl complexes and their products has been demonstrated by various examples. This article highlights various types of substitution reactions of $W(CO)_6$ with various ligands and shows a few examples of what is being done in the area as we change to our work of the future.

Keywords: Complexes, Metal Carbonyl, substitution Reaction, Carbon monoxide, Catalysts, Organometallic.

Introduction

Tungsten hexacarbonyl $[W(CO)_6]$, is prepared by the reduction of WCl_6 under a pressure of carbon monoxide¹. It is highly soluble in non-polar organic solvents. This colorless compound is a volatile, air-stable derivative of tungsten in its zero oxidation state. All reactions of $W(CO)_6$ commence with displacement of CO ligands. Coordination of $W(CO)_5$ with P(I)/P(III) results in stabilization of their compounds².

Reactions for Tungsten hexacarbonyl $[W(CO)_6]$:

(A) A reaction of t-BuLi with 4-Bromo-1-iodo-reductive demetalation reactions to afford 3,4,5,6-1,3-butadienes followed by addition of $W(CO)_6$, tetrapropyl- 2H-pyran-2-one in excellent yield³. results in the formation of metapyranylidenes. These pyranylidene carbene complexes undergo

(B) Photochemical reaction of $W(CO)_6$ with diethylsilane in presence of olefin (Norbornene) in *n*-heptane solution, generates stable complex $[W(CO)_5(\eta^2\text{-toluene})]$ and Poly-NBE⁴.

(C) Aldol-type condensation reactions of cyclic, acyclic and substituted cyclic ketones are promoted by $W(CO)_6$ in presence of UV light to afford 2-cycloalkylidencycloalkanone⁵.

(D) SF_6 -photosensitised IR laser pyrolysis of acetones with $W(CO)_6$ in the gas phase at moderate temperatures affords a simple, clean and low-energy route to gas phase carbene chemistry⁶.

(E) $W(CO)_6$ effectively catalyses the cyclotrimerization of *N*-cyanopiperidine to afford 2,4,6-tripiperidino-1,3,5-triazine in excellent yields, in toluene under heating conditions⁷.

(F) Synthesis of C-5 substituted Hydantoin from the corresponding α -amino amides by $W(CO)_6$ catalysed oxidative carbonylation using I_2 as oxidant. These Hydantoin shows wide range of biological properties in medicinal chemistry⁸.

(G) Oxidative carbonylation of *p*-substituted arylamines to symmetrical *N,N*-diaryl ureas by using $W(CO)_6$ as the catalyst, I_2 as the oxidant, CO as the carbonyl source and 4-dimethylamino-pyridine (DMAP) as base^{9a}. Hydroxyalkylureas were obtained under similar conditions using amino alcohols^{9b}.

(H) Photoirradiation of a solution of N-(-2-(Prop-1-ynyl)phenyl)pyrrolidine and $[\text{W}(\text{CO})_6]$ in toluene in presence of 5-Å molecular sieves and Et_3SiH at room temperature gave tricyclic indole derivative and Et_3Si -substituted indole derivative¹⁰.

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